

INTERACTIVE E-BOOK ON DIGESTIVE SYSTEM: A NEEDS ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Filipino students consistently rank low in science literacy compared to other countries (Allan et al., 2023). According to the results of PISA 2022, the Philippines ranked among the lowest performers among the 81 countries that participated in the assessment. In science, the Philippines ranked 80th with an average score of 356 points, which is still lower than the OECD average of 485 points. This study is primarily focused on conducting a needs assessment to obtain valuable insights regarding the potential development of an interactive eBook on digestive system. This study will employ a mixed method design which includes qualitative and quantitative. To gather the necessary data for this study, a validated survey questionnaire with open-ended questions intended for science teachers who are teaching the topic and Grade 9 students who took the subject in their previous years was employed. Their responses are crucial for the design and development of the material. Results suggest that there is a need among teachers and positive interest among students for the development of the said interactive eBook to enhance teaching and learning experience.

Keywords: *Interactive e-book, Development, Digestive System, Grade 8 Learners*

INTRODUCTION

Existing studies showed that teaching the topic "digestive system" in a regular classroom setting poses challenges for several reasons. Firstly, students may find it

difficult to visualize and comprehend the process of digestion since it is a process that takes place within the body and is not readily apparent (Mack et al., 2023). Moreover, the abstract nature of the concepts pertaining to the digestive system entails a challenge for students to comprehend and for teachers to make more tangible during instruction (Tapia et al., 2023). In addition, students frequently possess different notions and misunderstandings regarding the digestive process, such as the belief that digestion stops in the stomach or that mechanical process exclusively takes place in the mouth (Khastini et al., 2022). These alternative ideas impede students' comprehension and need focused training to supplant them with scientific notions (Çakmak & Bulunuz, 2022). Hence, the difficulty in teaching this subject is further compounded by the fact that there is a lack of comprehension of the cellular and molecular parts of digestion, as well as the contrast between the macro and micro levels of digestion. For this reason, innovative teaching strategies and approaches that leverage the use of technology and multimedia are needed to enhance the student's understanding on this topic.

Interactive e-books have become essential in education since they offer a more captivating and individualized learning encounter for students. According to a study about the adoption of interactive E-books in teaching K-12 students published by Zhang et. al. (2021), interactive e-books can be easily customized according to students' reading style and provide annotation support, which allows students to edit, add notes, or highlight specific text without harming the original work. An advantage of interactive e-books is their capacity to offer immediate response. Students are provided with prompt feedback on their choices and behaviors, enabling them to contemplate their cognitive processes and gain insights from errors. This real-time feedback enhances the learning experience, reinforcing critical thinking skills through continuous self-assessment and improvement. Additionally, interactive e-books can contain visual content, audio, and animations making the learning process more interesting and fun. Most importantly, these materials can be accessed on various devices, including smartphones, tablets, and laptops, making them easily accessible for students. They also offer features such as definitions, examples, and practice exercises that help students understand and apply concepts effectively.

The researchers found out that there are only limited studies that explore the potential of interactive eBooks in teaching biology specifically in the topic digestive system. The researchers also observed that these existing interactive eBooks need access to the internet to be able to utilize it. With that in mind, the researchers aim to develop an interactive eBook which can be utilized even without the use of internet. Hence, this investigation is important because it has the potential to provide benefits for both students and educators who are continually searching for novel and successful techniques to improve the teaching and learning experience in science education.

Research Objectives

Specifically, this study aims to:

Conduct a needs analysis to identify teachers' and students' experiences, challenges, and preferences in the Digestive System topic.

METHODOLOGY

Research Setting

The study took place on three selected public high schools across the division of Lanao del Norte namely: (1) Kapatagan National High School, (2) Lala National High School, and (3) Lanao del Norte National Comprehensive High School.

Research Participants

The main participants of this study are the Science Teachers and the Grade 9 Learners. In collecting the teachers' experiences and challenges, a total of ten high school Science/Biology teachers was purposefully selected. Similarly, in collecting the students' challenges and preferences, a total of twenty was purposefully selected. Grade 9 learners were chosen as student participant in this study as they already finished the topic on their previous year.

Research Instruments

Survey Questionnaire for Teachers

A survey questionnaire was employed to collect information regarding the teachers' experiences and challenges in delivering the topic. This questionnaire consists of three sections. Part A (Personal Information) gathers data about the teacher's demographics and years of experience. Part B (Teaching the Digestive System) is a 10-item questionnaire that gathers information about the teacher's familiarity with the topic and the instructional materials they are using. Lastly, Part C (Challenges), consists of two open-ended questions that aim to gather more insights about the challenges they have encountered in teaching the subject matter.

Survey Questionnaires for Students

Similarly, a survey questionnaire was employed to collect information concerning the student's misconceptions, challenges, and preferences in learning the topic Digestive

System. The survey questionnaire is composed of twenty questions regarding the common misconceptions in learning the topic (five items), their challenges (six items), interest and engagement (two items), resources and support available (two items), preference in the instructional method (four items), and overall experience in learning the topic (one item). It also has two open-ended questions that aims to gather more insights about the challenges they have encountered in learning the subject matter.

Data Analysis

In analyzing the data that were gathered, different methods and statistical tools were utilized. Weighted mean computation was used to analyze the data acquired from the rating scales. Additionally, a thematic analysis was performed on the open-ended questions responses.

Scope and Limitations

The scope of this study is to conduct a thorough needs assessment in order to guide the creation of an interactive e-book centered around the digestive system by identifying the teachers' and students' challenges and preferences in teaching and learning the topic.

RESULTS

Table 1

Evaluation on Teachers Challenges in teaching the Digestive System

Teaching the Digestive System	Mean	Description
1. I think that the topic "Digestive System" is important.	4.9	Strongly Agree
2. I often encounter student misconceptions about the digestive system (e.g. digestion stops in the stomach)	4.2	Agree
3. I find it challenging to find materials/tools to visualize the process of the digestive system in teaching.	3.2	Neutral
4. I am very familiar with the cellular and molecular parts of digestion.	3.5	Neutral
5. I feel confident regarding my ability to effectively teach the topic digestive system to the students.	4.5	Agree
6. I provide students with engaging materials that enhance their scientific literacy in the topic Digestive System.	3.3	Neutral
7. I use non-electronic (printed) books/modules in my teaching.	4.1	Agree
8. I use electronic books (e-books) in my teaching.	2.3	Disagree

9. I believe that the current curriculum and teaching resources sufficiently facilitate my instruction on the digestive system.	3.6	Agree
10. I think I need interactive teaching materials for the digestive system topic to enhance the student learning process.	4.8	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.84	Agree

Table 2

Summary of Responses for the Open-ended questions of Science Teachers on the challenges encountered in teaching the digestive system

Themes	Codes	Mentions	Sample Utterances
Challenges in teaching the topic	Lack of teaching resources	3	<p>STOE5: “The school doesn’t have enough learning materials and tools to improve the teaching like televisions or appropriate materials for the topic.”</p> <p>STOE1: “Some classrooms do not have television yet which limits the motivating factor in the delivery of the lesson.”</p> <p>STOE3: “Lack of materials to be used in teaching.”</p>
	Need for visual aids	2	<p>STOE2: “Modules and books are not enough for the students to learn in today’s generation, the aid of videos is very important and helpful.”</p> <p>STOE4: “Human torso is also needed.”</p>
	Student literacy and poor reading comprehension	1	<p>STOE8: “The truth is that most of the students can’t read. There are students that can read but poorly comprehend.”</p>
	No challenges encountered	1	<p>STOE7: “None so far”</p>
Coping Techniques	Utilization of multimedia	7	<p>STOE6: “I’ll find some videos that explain this topic from YouTube but these videos do not cover the topics very well.”</p> <p>STOE2: “ I download videos and make a PowerPoint presentation about the lesson. I also use the digestive system model from the science laboratory for students to visualize what is really inside our body.”</p>

Not applicable	1	<p>STOE5: "I give students some videos from YouTube and give simple illustrations like pictures."</p> <p>STOE7: "Not applicable since I did not have challenges in teaching the topic."</p>
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Table 3

Evaluation on Students' Challenges in learning the Digestive System in terms of Misconceptions

Misconceptions	Mean	Description
1. I believe food moves through the digestive system solely through gravity (e.g., food simply falls from the mouth to the stomach).	3.15	Moderately Agree
2. I think all digestion occurs in the stomach.	2.9	Moderately Agree
3. I believe the small intestine is responsible for storing waste before it is eliminated from the body.	3.8	Agree
4. I believe the large intestine's main function is to absorb nutrients from food.	4.05	Agree
5. I think the main purpose of the stomach is to absorb nutrients from food.	3.65	Agree
Overall Mean	3.51	Agree

Legend: 4.51–5.00 (Strongly Agree) ; 3.51–4.50 (Agree) ; 2.51–3.50 (Moderately Agree) ; 1.51–2.50 (Disagree) ; 1.00–1.50 (Strongly Disagree)

Table 4

Evaluation on Students' Challenges in learning the Digestive System in terms of Challenges

Challenges	Mean	Description
6. Understanding the specific functions of each part of the digestive system is challenging for me.	3.45	Moderately Agree
7. I find it difficult to remember the sequence of events that occur in the digestive system.	3.55	Agree
8. Visualizing the structures of the digestive system and their functions is challenging for me.	3.2	Moderately Agree
9. I find it challenging to differentiate between the functions of the different organs in the digestive system.	3.1	Moderately Agree

10. I struggle to connect theoretical knowledge about the digestive system to real-life examples.	3.3	Moderately Agree
11. Integrating the concept of enzymatic digestion is difficult for me.	3.9	Agree
17. I find it challenging to incorporate the notion of enzymatic digestion.	3.45	Moderately Agree
Overall Mean	3.42	Moderately Agree

Legend: 4.51–5.00 (Strongly Agree) ; 3.51–4.50 (Agree) ; 2.51–3.50 (Moderately Agree) ; 1.51–2.50 (Disagree) ; 1.00–1.50 (Strongly Disagree)

Table 5

Evaluation on Student's Challenges in learning the Digestive System in terms of Interest and Engagement

Interest and Engagement	Mean	Description
12. I find the topic of the digestive system interesting and relevant to everyday life.	4.35	Agree
13. Engaging in hands-on activities related to the digestive system helps me understand the concepts better.	4.55	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	4.45	Agree

Legend: 4.51–5.00 (Strongly Agree) ; 3.51–4.50 (Agree) ; 2.51–3.50 (Moderately Agree) ; 1.51–2.50 (Disagree) ; 1.00–1.50 (Strongly Disagree)

Table 6

Evaluation on Student's Challenges in learning the Digestive System in terms of Resources and Support

Resources and Support	Mean	Description
14. Having access to visual aids, such as diagrams and models, enhances my understanding of the digestive system.	4.6	Strongly Agree
15. I believe additional resources, such as videos and interactive simulations, would improve my learning experience.	4.15	Agree
Overall Mean	4.38	Agree

Legend: 4.51–5.00 (Strongly Agree) ; 3.51–4.50 (Agree) ; 2.51–3.50 (Moderately Agree) ; 1.51–2.50 (Disagree) ; 1.00–1.50 (Strongly Disagree)

Table 7

Evaluation on Student's Challenges in learning the Digestive System in terms of Preference

Preference	Mean	Description
16. I prefer learning about the digestive system through interactive activities and discussions rather than traditional lectures.	3.45	Moderately Agree
18. I believe that having an interactive e-book about the digestive system can improve my learning experience.	3.42	Moderately Agree
19. Interactive e-books can be accessed anywhere and are less hassle to carry	4.05	Agree
Overall Mean	3.9	Agree

Legend: 4.51–5.00 (Strongly Agree) ; 3.51–4.50 (Agree) ; 2.51–3.50 (Neutral) ; 1.51–2.50 (Disagree) ; 1.00–1.50 (Strongly Disagree)

Table 8

Evaluation on Student's Challenges in learning the Digestive System in terms of Overall Experience

Overall Experience	Mean	Description
20. I believe that learning about the digestive system is essential for my overall education.	4.65	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	4.65	Strongly Agree

Legend: 4.51–5.00 (Strongly Agree) ; 3.51–4.50 (Agree) ; 2.51–3.50 (Neutral) ; 1.51–2.50 (Disagree) ; 1.00–1.50 (Strongly Disagree)

Table 9

Summary of Responses (Open-ended) of Students on the challenges encountered in learning the digestive system

Themes	Codes	Mentions	Sample Utterances
Challenges in learning the topic	Differentiating the functions of each organ	9	<p>SSOE11: "...its quite hard for me to understand their functions as well."</p> <p>SSOE12: "Some challenges that I encountered while learning the digestive system are the different parts of it and its functions."</p> <p>SSOE14: "Differentiating between their functions and organs challenged me."</p>

Memorizing the names and functions of each organ	4	<p>SSOE2: “The challenges that I encounter in learning the topic “digestive system” are memorizing the functions of each organ”</p> <p>SSOE10: “The other challenges that I encounter while learning the topic digestive system is that memorizing the organs”</p>
Understanding complex concept	3	<p>SSOE3: “The other challenges I encountered in learning this topic is when the topic widened and went deeper and hard to understand.”</p> <p>SSOE6: “...some I can’t quite understand due to its complex structure.”</p>
Identifying effects due to neglection of an organ	1	<p>SSOE2: “The challenges that I encounter in learning the topic “digestive system” are memorizing the functions of each organ that are included in this system and identifying the effect of an organ when it is being neglected.”</p>
Identifying relationships between organs	1	<p>SSOE1: “The other challenges that I encounter in learning the topic digestive system is identifying if there is another organ or factor affecting another organ, as our lessons only taught the simple ones.”</p>
Briefly Explained	1	<p>SSOE16: “...it was just briefly explained.”</p>
No challenges encountered	3	<p>SSOE5: “I did not encounter any challenges in learning the topic digestive system.”</p>

Table 9

Summary of Responses (Open-ended) of Students on the challenges encountered in learning the digestive system (continued)

Themes	Codes	Mentions	Sample Utterances
Resources provided by the teacher in learning the topic	Videos	8	<p>SSOE4: “Videos are one of the materials we used...”</p> <p>SSOE5: “My teacher provides videos for us to visualize how the digestive system works.”</p>

Books and modules	7	<p>SSOE1: “The learning materials that my teacher provides in learning the topic digestive system are textbooks...”</p> <p>SSOE6: “But mainly our materials that our teacher provide are textbooks...”</p> <p>SSOE14: “Modules.”</p>
Pictures and Illustrations	5	<p>SSOE6: “majority of which are just illustration of the digestive tract”</p> <p>SSOE7: “The materials that my teacher provide is just the illustration of the digestive system of a human.”</p>
Models	5	<p>SSOE11: “The learning material that our teacher provided during the topic digestive system was a DIY model of how digestive system functions.”</p> <p>SSOE10: “The material that the teacher provide is a model.”</p> <p>SSOE6: “But rarely, we use models.”</p> <p>SSOE8: “Visual aids and models only.”</p>
Powerpoint presentations	3	<p>SSOE9: “Our teacher provides the learning materials using PowerPoint.”</p> <p>SSOE13: “Our teacher provided visual aids like PowerPoint.”</p>
Class discussions	3	<p>SSOE3: “...our teacher only discussed the topic.”</p> <p>SSOE4: “...discussion from our teacher.”</p>
Activity sheets	2	<p>SSOE16: “...an activity sheet to further decipher the topic.”</p> <p>SSOE15: “an activity involving the picture of said system in which we were tasked to name or label every organs.”</p>

DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows that teachers recognize the significance of the Digestive System topic and express assurance in their skills. However, there are evident areas for improvement in addressing student misconceptions, obtaining suitable instructional resources, and

integrating interactive and electronic teaching materials to enhance the teaching and learning process. These observations can provide guidance for specific interventions and assistance to enhance the efficacy of instruction in this crucial field of science education. Additionally, Table 2 shows that teachers expressed significant challenges in teaching the topic like the lack of teaching resources, need for visual aids, and poor reading comprehension of students. This scarcity of teaching resources not only affected the depth of teaching (Abdul, 2020) but also limited the range of teaching methods teachers could use (Suwartono & Aniuranti, 2018), ultimately impacting how well students understood the digestive system. There are also coping techniques identified to address these challenges however, the lack of interactive e-books as a teaching tool is apparent. Teachers voiced worries about the quality and breadth of the available online videos, which led to the need of adding basic graphics and images. Hence, the need for a coherent material that combines videos, detailed illustrations, interactive quizzes, and engaging activities in one output that can be accessed anywhere even without Wi-Fi is a necessary upgrade in the field of biology education.

Table 3 to table 8 shows that students have several common misconceptions regarding the digestive system (Tapia et al., 2023). Also, students have difficulty in understanding and comprehending the digestive system due to its abstract and complex nature (Uskola, 2024). The results also show that students perceive the topic as meaningful and applicable, recognizing its importance in understanding human health, nutrition, and overall well-being (Subiantoro & Mutiarani, 2021). They also expressed high level of agreement that participating in practical tasks pertaining to the digestive system enhances their comprehension of the concepts. Regarding resources and support, it is clear that students greatly appreciate visual aids and additional resources that reinforce their understanding and enrich their educational experience. This highlights a desire for additional learning materials that are capable of delivering dynamic and interactive learning of the complex processes that occur within the digestive system (Agustina et al., 2022), as these tools have the potential to facilitate deeper engagement among students and retain essential concepts. Several insights also emerge regarding students' highly positive attitude on innovative instructional methods and resources. This indicates an optimistic attitude of leveraging digital resources to augment conventional teaching materials (Indrawan et al., 2023), maybe offering more interactive content catered to different learning preferences (Junger et al., 2023).

Moreover, Table 9 shows the summarized responses of the students from the open-ended part of the survey about the challenges they encountered in learning the topic digestive system. Two themes were determined which are: (1) challenges in learning the topic; and (2) resources provided by the teacher in learning the topic. Under the first theme, seven codes were determined. These codes are differentiating the functions of each organ, memorizing the names and functions of each organ, understanding complex concepts, identifying effects due to neglect of an organ, identifying relationships between organs, briefly explained, and no challenges encountered. While on the second theme, seven were also identified. These are videos, books and modules, pictures and illustrations, models, PowerPoint presentation, class discussions, and activity sheets. Still, it is interesting that these sites lack the utilization of innovative materials like

interactive e-books. The discovered reliance on several multimedia tools emphasizes the requirement of a comprehensive, interactive e-book especially meant to combine these components in one output. Such an e-book would simplify access to digital visual aids, illustrations, interactive elements, and structured content, therefore improving the learning process and tackling the difficulties students have in learning the digestive system.

Conclusions

To summarize, the needs analysis uncovers substantial deficiencies in the existing instructional resources and approaches employed for instructing the digestive system. Despite the teachers' various coping strategies, the absence of interactive e-books is evident, implying the necessity for a comprehensive, integrated teaching tool. The development of an interactive e-book combining videos, thorough drawings, interactive quizzes, and interesting and practical activities could greatly improve the teaching and learning process. This material would address the demands of teachers as well as students, fostering improved comprehension of the digestive system and strengthening biology teaching.

Recommendations

Considering the discussions that emerged from the results of this study, it is strongly recommended that an interactive e-book on the digestive system be developed and implemented for students.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study thoroughly addressed ethical considerations and concerns in accordance with the established guidelines of the University before it started. Appropriate permission from the competent governing bodies was requested. A letter of consent was forwarded to the Division's Office and Principals Office, informing them of the intent of the study. Moreover, a letter of consent was also attached to the questionnaire that the participants completed. The consent specified the goal and purpose of the study and the approximated amount of time required to complete the questionnaire. Furthermore, to safeguard the privacy of the participants, no extraneous personal information was solicited. It was ensured that there was no harm to the participants while conducting the survey, and finally, the data was treated with the utmost confidentiality.

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